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COURSE CODE: ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. How to avoid plagiarism?

- In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using.¹**
- The writer must copy the author.
- The writer must have the authorization of the author.
- The writer must never cite any author.

2. What is the meaning of CMS?

- Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). CMS is a simple style for writing theses, scientific and academic articles.²**
- Common Medical Science.

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University 2019), 6.

² Ibid., 24.

- Chicago Medical Style.
- Chicago Minister of Science.

3. **Your first obligation as researcher is?**

- To cite your sources accurately and fully so that your readers can find them.³**
- To write very good.
- To have a manageable topic.
- To give good recommendations.

4. **Why reasons need the support of evidence?**

- A reason is abstract, and you don't have to cite its source (if you thought of it). Evidence usually comes from outside your mind, so you must always cite its source.⁴**
- A reason is the work of the writer.
- Evidence is more important than reason.
- Reason and evidence are different.

5. **The citation of legal case follows specific rules.**

- Give the full case name, name of the reporter (abbreviated; see below), ordinal series number (if applicable), opening page number of the decision, abbreviated name of the court and date (together in parentheses), and other relevant information, such as the name of the state or local court (if not identified by the series title). Actual**

³ Turabian, Kate L., 8th ed. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 25.

⁴ Ibid., 34.

pages cited follow the opening page number, separated by a comma.⁵

- The name of the case, the court and the judge.
- The name the court and the date.
- All information.

6. In writing your dissertation, your intention is?

- Not only to demonstrate your knowledge of the topic. You also want to capture the interest of and guide the reader throughout so that she or he understands and can follow your train of thought.⁶**
- Demonstrate your capacity of writing and knowledge.
- Demonstrate your wisdom.
- Give the readers an information.

7. The goal of the researcher is?

- To tell a story that should be vivid and interesting while also accurate and credible. In your report, the events, the people, and their words and actions are made explicit so that readers can experience the situation as real in a similar way to the researcher and experience the world of the participants.⁷**
- To tell story simply.
- To help the readers to make a similar experience.

⁵ Ibid., 125.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 21.

⁷ Ibid., 127.

To help readers to write.

8. **The starting point of any research project.**

The starting point for any research project, and indeed the first major challenge in conducting research, involves coming to some decision about a sound, doable topic.⁸

Is the data management.

The question about the topic.

The love of the research.

9. **The dissertations and theses are cited in the order.**

In the same manner as other unpublished manuscripts but add a parenthetical after the date to indicate the type of work and the institution that awarded the degree.⁹

In the same order of book.

Of author and date.

Any order.

10. **When an authenticated, official, or exact copy of a source is available online.**

⁸ Ibid., 5.

⁹ Prince, Mary Miles, 19th ed. *The BlueBook, A Uniform System of Citation*. (Massachusetts: Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 160.

- Citation can be made as if to the original print source (without any URL information appended).¹⁰
- Citation can be made following any style.
- Citation can be made like a citation of the book.
- Citation can be made with any URL information.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Second edition. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

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¹⁰ Ibid., 169.